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**THE IMPACT OF GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN
BOTSWANA FROM 1990-2021**

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CHAPTER 1

1.1 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Government expenditure refer to as the money government spends towards supply of goods and services that are not provided by the private sector but are important for the welfare of the nation. Government expenditure can also refer to the purchase of goods and services, which include public consumption and public investment, and transfer of payments consisting of income transfers (pensions, social benefits) and capital transfer. According to Breton 2018 public expenditure can be defined as ‘The expenditure incurred by public authorities like central, state and local governments to satisfy the collective social wants of the people ’’

Economic growth refers to an increase in the size of a country's economy over a period of time. The size of an economy is typically measured by the total production of goods and services in the economy, which is known as gross domestic product (GDP). Todaro (1995) defined economic growth as a long-term increase in a country's capacity to supply increasingly diverse economic goods to its population, with this growth based on advancing technology and the institutional and ideological changes that it usually entails.

Foreign Direct Investment refers to the investment made by individuals, businesses, or entities from one country into another country. FDI plays a crucial role in promoting economic growth by bringing in capital, technology, and expertise to the Botswana. It serves as a source of external financing, contributing to the expansion of productive capacities, job creation, and technology transfer. FDI can have a significant impact on economic growth by stimulating domestic investment, enhancing productivity, and fostering innovation and competitiveness in the host economy. Foreign direct investment is discussed because I included it as a part of my objectives to establish the relationship between itself, government expenditure and economic growth.

Economic growth can be measured in nominal or real terms. Nominal economic growth refers to the increase in the dollar value of production over time. This includes changes in both the volume of production and the prices of goods and services produced. Real economic growth, which economists prefer using most, increases in the volume produced only, taking

away the effect of prices changing. Real economic growth is a better measure because it reflects how much a country is producing at a given time, compared with other points in time.

Gross domestic product is a type of an economic tool that is utilized by governments and economists as a means of measuring or attributing a value to the final goods and related services within a defined economy in a stated period. The measurement of GDP is used to calculate the living standards in a country due to its importance in the calculation of how well the economy is performing. As such the relationship between GDP and economic growth is the fact that GDP serves as a means for analyzing how an economy is behaving. This link between GDP and economic growth is drawn from the fact that the GDP seeks to measure the total consumption of goods and services within the economy, a factor that helps shed light on the state of the economy under consideration. When measuring the GDP, the only consideration are the final goods, meaning that raw materials that have been used in the production of the final goods will not be included in this calculation. Otherwise, it would lead to misleading information based on the fact that raw material would have been counted twice. As such the measurement of GDP would only be based on the finished product, and the number of such consumables can be the basis for the measurement of how well the economy performed during the period under consideration, which also establishes a link between GDP and economic growth. During the calculation of the GDP as part of the process of establishing the link between GDP and economic growth, the analysis can be divided into time periods, which may be based on quarterly assessments, yearly assessments or four-year assessments. Whatever the case, when the consumption within that period is high, it shows that the economy is performing according to expectations. When the consumption is low, this may be the basis of concern due to the negative macroeconomic effects. Even though consumption is necessary to maintain the economic balance, an excessive rate of consumption can have the opposite effect as it may result in inflation.

There are different measures that can be used to determine GDP in an economy:

Real Gross Domestic Product which accounts for the value of goods and services produced, that means the sum of all goods Batswana are selling, together with the value of intangibles/services they provide minus the effects of inflation. Gross Domestic Product per capita measures the value of goods and services if it were divided equally among every person in a country. Whereas GDP growth measures the difference in GDP from one year, or one three-month period, to the next

Government spending helps to create a favourable environment for trade with other countries. Trade liberalization and openness are promoted as critical prescriptions for achieving high economic growth. The provision of better conditions has been the sole responsibility of the government since the time of classical economists.

In African countries, like any other developing economies, the government is usually regarded as the largest spender of money and this trend has continued to rise on the average due to the increased demand for public goods such as roads, communication, power, defence, education, health and other infrastructure that complement private sector productive activities. Available statistics show that total government expenditure and its components have continued to rise in the last two decades based on the premise that the countries in Africa have a weak infrastructural base, hence government has to play a greater role in stimulating and engendering economic growth in the face of market imperfections.

Government expenditure plays a significant role in determining the levels of economic growth in an economy because the government's expenditure policies reveal its objectives and priorities. As an important tool, government spending can contribute to a country's economic progress, especially Botswana. It also indicates the occurrence of economic expansion, as economic growth is closely related to the long-term economic position. In addition, government spending is a crucial aspect that must be increased in order to maintain high levels of economic growth. This is due to the fact that government spending is a key component that may be used to help the economy recover (Abdullah, 2010) Setting budget targets, adjusting taxation, increasing public expenditure, and public works are all very effective tools for influencing economic growth.

Government expenditure is an important aspect of a country's growth and development in terms of business progression and long-term economic development. The level of asset ventures that significantly impact economic growth and development has a positive impact on the economic growth of developing countries such as Botswana. For these nations, we can deduce that as investment within a nation's borders increases, so will productively output and economic growth. The main goal of Economic Growth is to alleviate persistent poverty while also providing hope for societal improvement (kukar, 2011).

According to Musgrave the demand for public service tends to be very low when per capita income is low. The assertion is due to him, such income is dedicated to fulfilling primary needs, and when per capita income begins to rise above low-income levels, demand for the

public sector provision of utilities such as health, education, and transportation begins to rise, forcing government spending on them to increase. Per capita income has a high correlation with public sector social service demand with supply. So, as Africa has experienced sustained growth in the last 30 years [except during corona virus disease (COVID-19) lockdown], social demand for public goods has risen and the size of the public sector has been forced to increase its activities. One key implication is that pressure remains on the government to provide public goods, which the current state has remained behind the required amount, leading to the infrastructural deficit, high out of school children, poor health, etc., in Africa. The state of socio-economic outcomes in Africa is by far below expectations as a result of a deficit in these public goods, among others. Unarguably, high quality of life may be achieved with increased government spending. Meanwhile, poverty continues to be prevalent, with large inter-country and intra-country disparities, particularly in West, East, Southern, and Central Africa as a group. Likewise, manufacturing and value addition in most countries in Africa remain weak due in part to constrained infrastructure and the prevalence of racially biased cultural norms that strengthen their behaviour. The core objective of the government is to promote well-being through allocation, distribution, stabilization, and economic growth, and as such government must spend. The quality of government spending in Africa has become more important due to the higher demand for public goods or services and uncertain external development assistance. Having experienced a growing expenditure pattern in Africa over the years with low government performance, the efficiency of government spending, therefore, becomes essential.

Kebaabetswe (2014) focused on examining the impact of FDI on economic growth in Botswana. The findings indicated a positive relationship between FDI and economic growth in Botswana. The study suggested that FDI inflows have played a significant role in promoting economic growth by stimulating investment, generating employment opportunities, and transferring technology and knowledge.

Makochekanwa (2012) empirically investigated the relationship of Foreign Direct Investment and Economic Growth in Botswana: This study was to investigate the relationship between FDI and economic growth in Botswana. It examines the impact of FDI on economic growth using empirical analysis.

The study concluded a positive and significant relationship between FDI and economic growth in Botswana. The study concludes that FDI inflows have contributed to the economic growth of the country.

Keynes (1936) developed the concept of the importance of government spending for economic growth, arguing that economic growth increased government spending. The efficient use of public resources can boost the economy's productive capacity and growth. Detractors of the Keynesian hypothesis (Barro, 1990) argued that increased government spending can be a hinderance to growth, and that it has the potential to reduce growth by crowding out private sector spending, particularly if the spending is funded through borrowing.

Increasing government spending stimulates aggregate demand in a stagnant economy. According to Keynesian economics, governments can try to overcome depression by borrowing from the private sector and increasing economic spending, which will have a multiplier effect (Sachs and Larrain, 1993). Keynes argued that government spending stimulates economic activity by increasing purchasing power. As a result, people would spend more, boosting overall economic growth through the multiplier effect.

However, proponents of endogenous growth models, such as Barro (1990), believe that only productive government expenditures, such as infrastructure development, will have a long-term positive effect on a country's growth rate. Endogenous growth economists attribute increases in national productivity to faster-paced innovation and human capital investment. They argue that government and private sector institutions should invest more in health and education to foster innovation and provide incentives for economic agents to be incentive-driven (Iheoma, 2012). Others, such as Mitchel (2005), believe that increases in government spending led to a drop in a country's economic performance. It is therefore important to empirically investigate whether or not, public spending in education and health impact positively on growth

Botswana is frequently cited as an example of an African poster economy, demonstrating how good governance and efficient utilization and management of its natural resource revenues have transformed the economy into one of the continent's most stable (World Bank, 2018). Since independence and the discovery of diamonds in the 1970s, the economy has evolved from a primarily subsistence agricultural-based economy with a per capita income of around \$360 in 1968 to \$7482 in 2017. (World Bank, 2018). As the economy grew, so did

government spending. Total government spending as a percentage of GDP averaged around 30% of GDP between 1985 and 1999, and around 40% of GDP between 2000 and 2016. (Bank of Botswana Annual Statistics, 2002-2017). Sustained economic growth has been a key tenet of the country's National Development Plans (NDPs). Government expenditure is consistently stated as an important component in the country's domestic expenditures (NDP, 11) "as a measure to upsurge employment creation through increased domestic aggregate demand.

Botswana has experienced the fastest rates of per capita income growth since independence. From 1967 to 2006, annual economic growth averaged 9%. It did, however, contract during the global recession of 2008-2009. Since the discovery of diamonds in the 1970s, Botswana's economic growth has been largely driven by the mining sector, particularly diamond revenues. According to BIDPA, diamond mining accounted for more than a third of GDP in 2014 and 70-80 percent of export earnings (2015). Manufacturing, tourism, construction, financial services, and agriculture are also important industries.

The global economic crisis, which reduced demand for diamonds, caused the economy to contract by 7.65 percent in 2009. The economy did recover from the economic crisis, registering a robust growth of 9.32 percent in 2013 as a result of returned activity in the mining sector. However, growth slowed down again in 2014 to about 4.3 percent GDP per capita growth due to a small overall growth in the non-mining activities. Particularly the water and electricity supply sector which declined sharply because of the supply challenges it experienced and measures taken to address them

Since Botswana has an evident growing GDP, therefore it has well established economic growth which can be traced through rural electrification projects, devolution, infrastructural projects in rural areas and youth funds, empowering of women through devolution, better healthcare, free education system initiated.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Botswana's economy has been largely driven by mineral resources, particularly diamonds, for the past four decades. On average, the mining sector contributed about 38% of GDP, with diamonds accounting for at least 90% of total mining exports. Basdevant (2008) It is also

worth noting that revenue share and taxes from diamond mining account for approximately 30% of government revenues. However, diamonds are non-renewable resources, and it is expected that the country's diamond reserves, as well as diamond-related fiscal revenues, will decline substantially over the next decade. According to Basdevant (2008), Botswana's diamond reserves are likely to be depleted by the late 2020s. As diamond reserves decline, fiscal revenues are expected to fall significantly, potentially affecting per capita government spending and development. Given the expected fiscal revenue contraction, it is imperative that the country assess its management of public finances, with a view to improving the quality or productivity of government expenditure. This was also emphasized in World Bank (2010). Through analysis of the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Botswana, this study contributes to the debate on this important policy issue.

Foreign Direct Investment plays a crucial role in Botswana's economic development and has been a key driver of the country's growth. Botswana has actively pursued policies to attract foreign investment and create a conducive environment for FDI inflows. Botswana is known for its political stability, strong governance, and investor-friendly policies, making it an attractive destination for foreign investors. According to Makochekanwa (2012) the country has implemented measures to promote transparency, protect property rights, and facilitate ease of doing business, all of which have helped to create a favourable investment climate. Botswana's rich mineral resources, particularly diamond deposits, have been a significant factor in attracting foreign investment. The diamond mining sector has been a major recipient of FDI, with multinational mining companies establishing operations in the country. Botswana has recognized the need to diversify its economy beyond the mining sector. Efforts have been made to attract FDI in sectors such as tourism, manufacturing, agriculture, and services. The government has implemented policies to encourage investment in these sectors and create opportunities for economic diversification..

1.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

Main objective:

- i. To analyze the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Botswana for the period 1990-2021

Specific objectives:

- i. To discuss the role of foreign direct investment in the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth.
- ii. To derive policy implications for the design of policies to improve productivity of government spending from the empirical results.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTION

Main research question:

What is the impact of government expenditure on the economic growth of Botswana?

Specific Research Questions:

- i. What is the impact of foreign direct investment on the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth in Botswana?
- ii. What policy implications can be derived from empirical results and be used in the design of policies to improve productivity of government spending?

1.5 HYPOTHESIS

Null Hypothesis

- i. Government expenditure has no effect as a driver of economic growth in Botswana
- ii. There is no significant interaction effect of foreign direct investment on the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth in Botswana.

Alternative hypothesis

- i. There is a positive relationship between government expenditure and economic growth.
- ii. Foreign direct investment plays a significant role in strengthening the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth in Botswana.

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

The purpose of this study is to examine empirically the impact of government expenditure on economic growth focusing on Botswana's public expenditure data from 1990 to 2021 as a developing nation.

It is mandatory by the university (BA ISAGO) that every student enrolled for degree program to conduct a research project to be given their degree certificate. It gives the researcher being the student the ability to apply what they learnt here in school as theory, practically. It helps improving the researchers' professional reputation as well as increase their knowledge regarding the issues of economic growth and government expenditures. Lastly it is a requirement in the partial fulfillment of a Bachelor of Commerce in Economics.

This research on the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Botswana holds significant relevance for policymakers, economists, and stakeholders involved in the country's development. The findings of this study can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of government expenditure as a policy tool for stimulating economic growth. Understanding the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth can inform evidence-based decision-making, enabling policymakers to optimize resource allocation and prioritize investments in key sectors. By identifying the factors that contribute to sustainable economic growth, this study has the potential to guide the formulation of

targeted policies and strategies that can foster long-term economic development in Botswana. The outcomes of this research may contribute to the overall understanding of economic dynamics and provide a foundation for future studies and discussions on optimal resource utilization, investment strategies, and the role of government in driving economic growth

1.7 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study covers the period 1990 - 2021. This period is important in that it is when the country experienced significant increases in government spending.

1.8 LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

The study may manage to produce results that are in line with economic theory, whilst failing to disaggregate government expenditures into recurrent, capital or both components have impact on economic growth.

The use of secondary data which is prone to personal biasness limits the study since the data cannot be fully relied on due to personal errors and biasness. The study is tedious since I have to use more than thirty observations. This makes the analysis of the data to be more complicated and tiresome.

This study focuses on the impacts of government expenditure on the economic growth of Botswana and this makes the thesis not to go beyond Botswana's boundaries.

The study scope is narrowed to a period 32years from 1990 to 2021.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The relationship between government spending and economic growth has received a lot of attention in recent years, as economists and politicians try to figure out how government spending affects economic growth. Due to the general lack of agreement on the results and conclusions reached, the outcome of their work has been more confusing than helpful. From a theoretical viewpoint, there are Keynesians who believe that government spending has a positive impact on economic growth; and Classical and Neoclassical who believe that government spending has a negative impact on economic growth Romer (1986) Lowenberg (1990). There are also those that found a middle ground where government spending is postulated to have a positive impact on economic growth up to a certain optimal threshold, above which the impact of government spending on economic growth turns negative (Barro, 1989).

Even on an empirical front, the possible impact of government spending on economic growth has been varied as well. Some studies have found the impact to be positive while others have found a negative impact). There are also some studies that concluded that government spending has no significant impact on economic growth.

2.2 THEORETICAL LITERATURE

2.2.1 WAGNER's LAW

Wagner (1893) established his law of increasing government expenditure expansion. According to the law, there is a relationship between government spending and economic growth, but the causality goes from economic growth to government spending. Wagner offers three major foundations for boosting government spending. As government tasks such as administrative and regulatory functions increased as a result of industrialization, private sector activities were replaced by public sector activities. Second, the necessity for governments to offer welfare services such as public health, education, old-age pensions, food subsidies, natural disaster relief, and environmental protection programs increased government spending. The third reason is that rising industrialization brings about technological development and the formation of massive corporations that tend to monopolize. As a result, governments will have to compensate for this outcome by providing social and merit goods from the budget. Wagner (1893) asserted that government spending is an endogenous factor influenced by the nation's economic growth. As a result, national income influences public spending. Wagner's arguments were based on research into Germany's economic progress, but they also apply to other developing and developed countries. According to Wagner, rising government expenditure was an inevitable aspect of his time's developing countries, commonly known as industrializing countries; the rule simply asserts that "public expenditure will increase if industrializing countries' per capita income rises." As a result, the implication of this law is that government spending will rise faster than economic growth.

2.2.2 INNOVATIVE GROWTH THEORY OF SCHUMPETER

Joseph Alois Schumpeter (1883-1950) made a substantial contribution to growth theory, primarily through his 1911 book "The Theory of Economic Development." Schumpeter popularized the term "innovation" in economics and redefined the role of the entrepreneur in terms of economic development. According to Schumpeter, the starting point was a state of pure equilibrium or a steady state of the economy. Economic changes, he believed, were the driving force behind growth. They were triggered by a variety of factors, including the unexpected discovery of new sources of supplies, but the main driver was entrepreneurial innovation, which resulted in development. In Schumpeter's perspective, the businessman and entrepreneur, innovator, and creative individual is the driving force of progress. He is recognized for his initiative, insight, and risk-taking. According to Schumpeter, monopoly is a good thing because it is obtained by the implementation of new combinations of factors of production, revolutionary improvements in technology, in production technology, the invention of new products, entering new markets, and so on (Lavrov (2006)). Schumpeter defined economic progress as the "carrying out of novel combinations," which he defined broadly as follows. Madison, M. (1982):

1. Introduction of new goods;

2. Introduction of new methods of production;
3. Opening a new market;
4. Conquest of a new supply of raw materials;
5. New organization of an industry.

These specific forms of economic changes he viewed as development.

2.2.3 KEYNESIAN THEORY

This theory is based on Keynes (1936). Keynesian economics promoted a mixed economy in which both the state and the private sector were considered to play an important role. Keynesian economics sought to provide solutions to what economists believed to be the failure of laissez-faire economic liberalism, which advocated those markets and the private sector operated best without state intervention. In Keynesian theory, macroeconomic trends could overwhelm the micro-level behaviour of individuals. The theory is based on the assumptions of:

The economy operates in the short run, salaries and prices are fixed, the money market is insignificant, taxation is solely in the form of lump-sum taxes, and both planned spending and planned saving are connected to income. Keynes emphasized the importance of aggregate demand for commodities as a driving factor in the economy, particularly during recessions. According to the theory, government policies might be employed to boost macroeconomic demand and combat high unemployment and deflation (Branson, 1989). Keynes felt that the government was responsible for assisting a country's recovery from a depression. When the government expanded its spending, citizens were encouraged to spend more since there was a greater amount of money in circulation. People would begin to invest more, and the economy would resume stability. A major finding of Keynesian economics was that there was no strong automatic tendency for output and employment to increase to full employment levels (Keynes, 1936). Keynes' theory has the following flaws: The theory gave rise to the phenomena known as "stop-go." In other words, during periods of high unemployment, the government would increase aggregate demand. This would cut unemployment while also increasing inflationary pressures, forcing the government to reduce aggregate demand once more. As a result, every "go" era was followed by a "stop" period, making long-term economic progress difficult. A second limitation of the Keynesian model is that it fails to take adequately into account the problem of inflation. Third, it tends to understate the influence of money on the real variables in the economy. A change in the money supply, only affects national income through its effects on the rate of interest.

2.2.4 PEACOCK AND WISEMAN'S POLITICAL CONSTRAINTS MODEL

Peacock and Wiseman (1890-1935) discovered the displacement effect by analyzing the time course pattern of public expenditure. This model is based on a political theory of government expenditure determination, which states that governments like to spend more money, citizens do not like to pay more taxes, and governments must pay attention to citizens' demands. The

model assumes that there is a level of taxation that can be tolerated and functions as a constraint on government behaviour. As the economy and consequently income increases, tax revenue at a steady rate rises, allowing government spending to grow in accordance with GDP (Peacock and Wiseman, 1961). During times of social upheaval, such as war, hunger, or any other large-scale societal disaster, the progressive upward trend in government spending would be altered (displaced upward). To support the increase in government spending, the government may be required to boost taxes levels, a policy considered acceptable by the people during times of crisis. This is known as the displacement effect (Peacock and Wiseman, 1961). There is also the inspection effect to consider. This is due to people's increased awareness of social concerns during times of disturbance. The government, therefore, expands its scope of services to improve these conditions, since people's perception of tolerable levels of taxation does not return to its former level, the government is able to finance these higher levels of expenditure originating in the expanded scope of government and debt charges. The net result of these two effects is occasional short-term jumps in government expenditure within a rising long-term trend (Peacock and Wiseman, 1961).

2.2.5 THE THEORY OF ROBERT SOLOW

Solow's theory was first stated in an article titled "A Contribution to the Theory of Economic Growth" (1956), and then expanded upon in the "Technical Change and Aggregate Production Function" (1957). (1957). The author received the Nobel Prize in Economics in 1987 for its development. Solow begins by assuming that equality of aggregate demand and aggregate supply is an essential condition for economic system equilibrium. His theory based aggregate supply on the Cobb-Douglas production function, which expresses the functional dependency between production volumes on the one hand and the elements used and their combinations on the other. Solow's theory can uncover links between three drivers of economic growth: investments, labor, and technical advancement. According to the theory, the savings rate is an important factor in determining the level of capital intensity. A higher savings rate results in a larger stock of capital, which leads to increased investment and, as a result, a higher level of output. Population expansion is one of the causes for ongoing economic growth in a stable economy, according to Solow's theory. However, if population expansion is not supported by an increase in investment, the capital stock per worker falls. Thus, R. Solow's thesis explains that countries with faster population growth rates have lower capital-labor ratios and, as a result, lower incomes. After investments and an increase in the number of workforces, technical advancement is the third source of economic growth. It should be highlighted that in neoclassical theory, technical advancement does not imply the substitution of human labor by machines, but rather qualitative changes in production, such as raising workers' educational levels, improving organizational structures, expanding production scales, and so on.

2.2.6 HUMAN CAPITAL THEORY

Schultz created the human capital theory in the 1960s to explain the economic gains of investing in health and education to boost agricultural output. The argument was extended to demonstrate the transmission mechanism from better education to increased productivity as a

significant benefit to the entire economy (Iheoma, 2014). Schultz's demonstrations revealed that in America, human capital contributed more to the economy than physical capital output, emphasizing the importance of human capital in the industrial process. Becker (1993) expanded on Schultz's ideas by arguing that spending on education, training, and health is an investment in human capital because individuals cannot be divorced from their skills, health, knowledge, or values in the same way that physical assets can. Thus, government expenditure on health and education can be considered as a key foundation for achieving balanced and sustainable economic growth. According to Amakom (2010), the core idea of human capital theory is that investing in human capital through education and health is a crucial component of economic success.

2.2.7 CROWDING OUT THEORY

In accordance with this theory established by Bacon and Eltis (1970), government interference leads to a drop-in private investment activity, which is known as 'crowding out.' The model's assumptions are as follows: market income equals production value; there is no nonmarket (government) sector in the economy; and taxes serve as channels of resources from the market sector to nonmarket (government) activity. Crowding out can be classified into two types. The first type is direct crowding out, in which the public sector takes resources that could otherwise be employed by the private sector (Trotman, 1997). Economic growth is predicted to be constrained if the public sector replaces the private sector. This displacement impact occurs immediately when the government spends taxation revenue to purchase resources that might otherwise be utilized by the private sector. The second type is indirect crowding-out, which occurs when government spending, taxing, and borrowing create disincentives to productive effort, such as working, saving, and investing (Trotman1997). When borrowing leads to rising interest rates or inflation, it creates disincentives to invest. The sale of government debt to finance public sector borrowing may cause interest rates to rise, crowding out private investment indirectly. This would occur if either increasing public sector borrowing raises interest rates or private sector investment is very interest-elastic, resulting in a drop in private investment. The limitations of this model include: The theory ignores the importance of public sector services as inputs to the private sector, particularly education, which is vital in developing labour-force skills, and there are, of course, various other determinants of interest rates in the economy in addition to the public sector. The theory is extremely useful in Botswana because the economy has both public and private sectors. The proportion of private sector is determined by the proportion of public sector. If the government increases its productive investment, the private sector will be squeezed out (Bailey, 2002)

2.2.8 MUSGRAVE-ROSTOW's THEORY

Based on this theory, government spending is a necessity for economic development, and its level is closely proportional to a country's stage of development. Public investment as a proportion of overall economic investment is shown to be high in the early stages of economic growth and development. The public sector provides social infrastructure overheads such as roads, transportation infrastructure, sanitation services, law and order,

health, education, and other human capital investments, all of which are required to prepare the economy for take-off into the middle stages of economic and social development Musgrave (1989). During the intermediate stages of growth, the government continues to deliver investment goods, but this time public investment supplements private investment growth. Market failures emerge during the two stages of growth, which can hinder the drive towards maturity, requiring an increase in government involvement to deal with these market failures. In the mass consumption stage, income programmes and welfare redistribution policies rise significantly in relation to other items of government spending, as well as in relation to GNP (Musgrave and Musgrave, 1989). 36 The approach ignores the productive expenditure of the public sector and assumes that the government is the primary determinant of growth, which may not always be the case (Brown et al., 1996)

2.2.9 THE ENDOGENOUS GROWTH THEORY

(Paul) Romer developed a new growth theory, the Endogenous growth theory, in the late 1980s and early 1990s, emphasizing the need for a new definition of human capital, the skills and knowledge that boost productivity. According to endogenous growth theory, the magnitude of savings is a significant component in defining an economy's long run growth rate. The theory highlights that there are constant returns to capital and that economies never reach a stable equilibrium since capital accumulation does not slow, but the rate of growth is mostly determined by the type of capital in which the country invested. Economic growth theory put emphasis on the importance of capital accumulation in the realization of economic growth, the stock of capital can increase the economic output in the long run, and government can increase the productive capacity of an economy by investing on physical investment like infrastructure.

2.2.10 MONETARIST THEORY

This theory emphasises the centrality of the money supply in affecting nominal GDP and the price level (Ahmed, 1999). Friedman (1956) demonstrated convincingly that high inflation rates were caused by fast increases in the money supply. Controlling the quantity of money was hence the key to successful policy. The model's foundations were: there is a long-run close relationship between changes in the money supply and changes in national income, without government intervention the economy will tend towards its "natural" rate of unemployment, velocity of circulation of money is predictable, money changes will only affect real national income indirectly, and the economy is in equilibrium at full employment. They were against government spending and believed that fiscal policy was ineffective in promoting economic progress. Monetary policy may perform better in areas where it could be useful. Excessive government spending ultimately hinders the functioning of free markets and may result in bureaucratic mess, unnecessary social programmes, and huge deficits (Cullison, 1993). The model's shortcomings include the following. First, monetary theory does not provide a thorough account of the complex phenomena of change, in which non-monetary elements play a substantial role.

2.3 EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

Landau (1983) discovered a positive association between the proportion of government expenditure in GDP and the rate of increase of real per capita GDP for 104 nations. Cooray (2009) examined the relationship between government spending, governance, and economic growth in 71 developed, developing, and transition countries using cross-sectional data from 1996 to 2003. The findings suggested that more government spending and improved governance could boost economic outcomes.

Ram (1986) examined the effect of government size on economic growth using cross-section data for a broader sample of 115 nations and time-series data (1960-1980) for 17 individual countries. For several nations, estimation was done using OLS and also on the basis of a first-order auto-regressive disturbance term (AR1). The main findings are as follows: first, the overall impact of government size on growth is positive in almost all cases; second, the (marginal) externality effect of government size is generally positive; and third, despite the fact that the number of time series observations for each country is relatively small, the overall impact of government size on growth is positive, there is a broad harmony between the estimates obtained from cross section and time-series data; and fourth, it is possible that the positive effect of government size on growth is stronger in lower income contexts.

Donald and Shuanglin (1993) examined the differential effects of several expenditure categories on economic growth in 58 nations. Their findings revealed that, whereas government spending on education and defence had a beneficial effect on economic growth, welfare spending has a negligible negative effect.

Bleaney et al. (2001) investigated the impact of government spending on economic development in 22 Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) nations using panel data from 1970 to 1995 and the OLS and General Least Squares (GLS) methodologies. They came to the conclusion that only constructive government spending has an effect on economic growth. They discovered that education and health were significant, despite accounting for a larger amount of public consumption. This study, however, did not concentrate on African countries. Furthermore, owing of its vulnerability to endogeneity, OLS is not the optimal approach for panel data.

Fan and Rao (2003) used the OLS approach to examine the impact of various types of government spending on total GDP growth in 43 developing countries between 1980 and 1998 and found varied results. Public expenditure on agriculture and health in Africa has been particularly effective in encouraging economic growth. Agriculture, education, and defence expenditures have all contributed favourably to Asia's economic growth. Health spending had a growth-promoting influence in Latin America. Structural adjustment policies stimulated growth in Asia and Latin America but not in Africa. In fact, structural adjustment efforts impede African economic development.

Mogotsi and Mupimpila (2003) examined the impact of government size on economic growth in Botswana from 1978 to 1998, using development expenditure as a proxy for government size. Based on the analysis, government size increased significantly from 1978 to 1995 but declined growth after 1995.

Al-zeaud (2009) used the vector auto regressive (VAR) model to examine the dynamic effects of fiscal policy on the Jordanian economy from 1992 to 2009. The results show that one positive structural shock in exports and government spending will have a positive impact on real GDP in the medium and long term. However, such a shock in government expenditure and exports causes both short-term and long-term inflationary pressure.

In Lebanon, Saad (2009) examined the effects of public expenditure by sector from 1962 to 2007. Using the Error Correction Model and Johansen cointegration techniques, the study focused on critical sectors such as agriculture, defence, education, and health. According to the study, education has a positive long-term impact on growth, whereas defence has a negative impact and agriculture and health are minor in explaining growth. In the short run, health and education hampered Lebanon's growth, whereas defence and agriculture had no effect.

Botshelo (2010) used ordinary least squares and ECM to examine the relationship between public spending and Botswana's long-run economic performance from 1974/75 to 2007/08. Total expenditure, recurring expenditures, development expenditures, the Consumer Price Index, terms of trade, tax revenue, other expenditures, and specific public expenditure components were all analysed (expenditures incurred in ministries and sectors for functioning of economy e.g., health, education, skills and development, defence, economic services and housing, urban and regional development). The findings revealed a negative relationship between total government expenditures and economic growth. The findings suggested that

spending on health, housing, urban and regional development, as well as education, skills, and development, had a negative effect on growth. Defence expenditures had a positive and significant impact and economic services had a positive but insignificant impact. Consumer price index and Terms of Trade also had a positive influence on growth. Tax Revenue however had an insignificant and negative impact on growth.

Mwangi (2010) reported that improved government expenditure on areas such as physical infrastructure development and education enhances economic growth, whereas areas such as foreign debt servicing, government consumption, and expenditure on public order and security, salaries and allowances harm the economy.

According to Ebiringa and Charles (2012), evaluating the impact of some priority sector spending on economic growth is crucial. In this regard, the research looked into the impact of government sectoral spending on Nigeria's economic growth. They estimated the variables using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and Error Correction Model (ECM). The data indicated that transportation and agriculture spending had a negative impact on economic growth. Defense, telecommunications, health, and education spending all contributed to Nigeria's economic growth.

Kapunda and Topera (2013) used the ordinary least squares method to examine the impact of sectoral, capital, and recurrent expenditures on Tanzanian economic growth from 1965 to 2010. The results indicated that investments in agriculture, health, and infrastructure had a favorable and significant impact on growth. Education had a little but unfavorable impact on growth.

Nkiru, P., and Izuchukwu, D. (2013) used time series analysis to examine the Nigerian government's overall education expenditure from 1977 to 2012. Their findings demonstrated that government investment on education has an impact on growth through fostering the development of a strong human capital foundation. Time series emphasizes short and long run relationships, whereas panel data emphasizes causality.

Adu and Ackah (2015) used the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique to analyse the link between disaggregated government spending and economic growth in Ghana from 1970 to 2010. They discovered that capital spending had a negative and considerable influence on growth in both the short and long run. Recurrent spending had a positive effect. Capital and labour also have a substantial positive impact on economic growth. The terms of

trade were found to have a considerable positive effect, but inflation hampered economic progress.

Eggoh, et al (2015) tested the relationship between human capital (measured by health and education related variables) and economic growth for 49 African countries from 1996-2010 applying cross sectional and dynamic panel techniques of estimation. Results showed that public spending on health and education have negative impact on economic growth, with human capital stock indicators (literacy rate and gross primary enrolment) having a slightly positive impact.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the empirical model adopted for the study. The variables to be used in the study are the economic growth which is the dependent variable in this study while Government expenditure is the independent variable, exports of goods and services, inflation rate and foreign direct investment are the additional independent variables. The data, the data sources and the methods to be used in data analysis are explained

3.2 RESEARCH APPROACH

This study is aimed at establishing the effects of government expenditure on economic growth in Botswana through a quantitative approach. Quantitative data will be used in the study to answer to the research questions posed in chapter one. The study will use data for the period of 1990 to 2021 for government expenditure and economic growth.

3.3 VARIABLES

3.3.1 ECONOMIC GROWTH

This is the dependent variable in the model and represented by the gross domestic product per capita growth. This is a measure of total output of a country that takes GDP and divides it by the total population. A rise in per capita GDP implies growth in the economy and also signals an increase in productivity.

3.3.2 GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURE

Government expenditure refers to the total amount of money spent by the government on various sectors and activities within an economy. This includes spending on public services such as education, healthcare, infrastructure development, defense, social welfare programs, and more (Musgrave & Musgrave, 1989)

3.3.3 EXPORTS OF GOODS AND SERVICES

Exports of goods and services represent the total value of goods and services produced within a country's borders that are sold to foreign buyers. According to Taylor(2014) it includes physical goods such as manufactured products, agricultural commodities, and natural resources as well as services such as tourism, transportation, and financial services that are provided to customers outside the country.

3.3.4 INFLATION RATE

The inflation rate is a measure of the percentage change in the average price level of goods and services in an economy over time. It indicates the rate at which the general level of prices is rising and the purchasing power of money is decreasing. Blanchard (2009) states that Inflation can be influenced by factors such as changes in aggregate demand, supply shocks, monetary policy, and market expectations.

3.3.5 FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT

According to Zejan et.al (1996) Foreign direct investment refers to the investment made by individuals, businesses, or governments from one country into another country. It involves the establishment or acquisition of lasting interest in enterprises operating outside the investor's home country. FDI includes activities such as setting up new businesses, expanding existing operations, or acquiring ownership in foreign companies. Foreign direct investment can contribute to economic growth by bringing in capital, technology transfer, job creation, and stimulating productivity and innovation.

3.4 MODEL SPECIFICATION

The mathematical explanation of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables is referred to as model specification. With a focus on sectorial spending, this section provides an econometric model for the relationship between government spending and economic growth in Botswana.

Firstly, I identify the dependent variable, which is the variable that I want to explain. In my case, the dependent variable is economic growth, which can be measured using a real gross domestic product (GDP). The independent variable that are included in my model are government expenditure.

This study has decided to use a linear regression model and the model can be defined as shown below.

The general form of your model could be:

$$\text{Economic growth} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{Government Expenditure} + \beta_2 * \text{Exports of Goods and Services} + \beta_3 * \text{Inflation Rate} + \beta_4 * \text{Foreign Direct Investment} + \varepsilon$$

Where:

- β_0 is the intercept or constant term
- Economic Growth represents the dependent variable, which can be measured using an appropriate indicator such as GDP growth rate or per capita income growth.
- Government Expenditure, Exports of Goods and Services, Inflation Rate, and Foreign Direct Investment are the independent variables of interest, representing the key factors you want to investigate.

- $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3,$ and β_4 are the coefficients or parameters to be estimated, indicating the magnitude and direction of the relationship between the independent variables and economic growth.
- ε is the error term, which represents the random variation in the dependent variable that is not explained by the independent variables.

The expected signs of the coefficients:

- Government expenditure is often expected to have a positive effect on economic growth. Increased government spending on sectors such as education, healthcare, infrastructure, and research and development can stimulate economic activity, create jobs, and enhance productivity. Therefore, a positive coefficient ($\beta_1 > 0$) for Government Expenditure would be expected.
- Exports play a crucial role in generating foreign exchange earnings and fostering economic growth. Higher levels of exports indicate increased international competitiveness and market access, which can lead to economic expansion. Consequently, a positive coefficient ($\beta_2 > 0$) for Exports of Goods and Services would be anticipated.
- The relationship between inflation and economic growth is more complex and can be influenced by several factors. High inflation rates can erode the purchasing power of consumers, reduce investment, and lead to resource misallocation. Therefore, a negative coefficient ($\beta_3 < 0$) for the Inflation Rate is generally expected. However, in some cases, a slight positive relationship ($\beta_3 > 0$) can be observed, known as the inflation threshold effect, where moderate inflation rates may be associated with higher economic growth.
- Foreign direct investment can bring capital, technology, and managerial skills into an economy, contributing to economic growth. Therefore, a positive coefficient ($\beta_4 > 0$) for Foreign Direct Investment would typically be expected.

Test for multicollinearity: Test for multicollinearity between the independent variables, which occurs when the independent variables are highly correlated with each other. Multicollinearity can cause problems with the estimation of the coefficients and lead to incorrect inferences.

Test for heteroscedasticity: Test for heteroscedasticity, which occurs when the variance of the error term is not constant across observations. Heteroscedasticity can cause problems with the estimation of the standard errors and lead to incorrect inferences.

Test for serial correlation: Test for serial correlation, which occurs when the error term is correlated with its lagged values. Serial correlation can cause problems with the estimation of the coefficients and lead to incorrect inferences.

3.4.1 TYPES OF DATA

Secondary data obtained will be used to conduct this research. This type of data is more cost effective and quick as data already exists. This study is based on secondary time series data of government expenditure and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in order to explain any relationship that may exist between levels of government expenditure and levels of economic growth as measured by levels of Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The annual data on the above variable's 1990 – 2021 will be used. The annual secondary data regarding the research topic and selected sectors will be collected so as to reach the objective intended to be attained in this research. This data will be obtained from The World Bank. The EViews software will be used to interpret the data.

3.5 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

3.5.1 KEYNESIAN THEORY

The theoretical framework of this study draws upon Keynesian economics to understand the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. Keynesian theory posits that government expenditure plays a crucial role in stimulating aggregate demand and influencing overall economic activity (Keynes, 1936). By examining the impact of government expenditure on economic growth, this study seeks to contribute to the understanding of how fiscal policies can influence macroeconomic outcomes.

Keynesian Economics and Government Expenditure: According to Keynesian theory, increased government expenditure can boost economic growth by directly increasing aggregate demand. As the government spends on sectors such as infrastructure, education, healthcare, and public services, it creates employment opportunities, increases income levels, and stimulates consumer spending (Blinder & Solow, 1973). This, in turn, leads to higher production levels and economic expansion.

The multiplier effect, a central concept in Keynesian economics, suggests that an initial increase in government expenditure can have a magnified impact on overall output and income through subsequent rounds of spending (Hansen, 1941). As government expenditure increases, it generates a chain reaction of higher consumer spending, increased business investment, and further job creation, ultimately driving economic growth.

Keynesian theory emphasizes the importance of countercyclical fiscal policy, particularly during periods of economic downturn. During recessions, governments can utilize expansionary fiscal policies by increasing government expenditure to stimulate economic activity and prevent or mitigate the negative effects of a recession (Alesina & Ardagna, 2009).

In the context of my study on the impact of government expenditure, exports, inflation, and foreign direct investment on economic growth in Botswana,

Barro (1990) extended existing endogenous growth models to incorporate government sector (government purchases of goods and services) into an economy's production function. This is done by adding public spending to Romer (1986)'s AK model. This means government spending is an input in the production function and it is this role which creates a potential positive relationship between the government and growth. The production function is defined as follows:

$$Y = f(G, X, I, F)$$

Where: Y represents economic growth or output G represents government expenditure X represents exports of goods and services I represents inflation rate F represents foreign direct investment

The production function suggests that economic growth is a function of government expenditure, exports, inflation rate, and foreign direct investment. The specific form and functional relationships within the production function will be examined through empirical analysis.

By estimating the coefficients of each variable, you can assess the individual and collective impacts on economic growth. The estimated coefficients will indicate the magnitude and direction of the relationship between each input variable and economic growth. This analysis will provide insights into the relative importance of government expenditure, exports, inflation, and foreign direct investment in driving economic growth in Botswana.

3.6 ESTIMATION TECHNIQUE

The estimation technique to be used in this study is a correlation test. The statistical technique to test for correlation here is a multiple linear regression.

3.6.1 MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION

A multiple regression is used to explore the relationship between one dependent variable and two or more independent variables. The purpose of a multiple regression model is to predict values of a dependent variable based on the values of the independent variable. This model is suitable for this study as we are testing the relationship between one dependent variable, Economic growth and two independent variables which are education and health care.

There are 3 major uses for multiple linear regression analysis:

- First it may be used to identify the strength of the effect that the independent variables have on a dependent variable.
- It can be used to forecast effects of changes; it helps us understand how much will the dependent variable change when we change the independent variables.

- Multiple linear regression analysis predicts trends and future values. It can be used to get point estimates.

It is through the above points a multiple linear regression was deemed fit for this particular study.

I will conduct my study using multiple linear regression analysis guided by the following steps.

1. Collect the data: As mentioned earlier, collect data on the variables of interest, including economic growth, government expenditure in Botswana from 1990 to 2021. This data can be obtained from various sources, including the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, and the Botswana government's statistical agency.
2. Prepare the data: Clean and prepare the data for analysis, including dealing with missing values, outliers, and any other data quality issues.
3. Specify the model: Specify the multiple linear regression model as follows:

$$\text{Economic Growth} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{Government Expenditure} + \beta_2 * \text{Exports of Goods and Services} + \beta_3 * \text{Inflation Rate} + \beta_4 * \text{Foreign Direct Investment} + \varepsilon$$

Where β_0 is the intercept, β_1 and β_2 , β_3 and β_4 are the coefficients for Government Expenditure, Exports, Inflation rate and foreign direct investment respectively, and ε is the error term.

4. Estimate the coefficients: Estimate the coefficients of the model using OLS regression in your chosen statistical software. The software will generate the estimated coefficients, standard errors, t-values, and p-values for each independent variable.

OLS works by minimizing the sum of the squared differences between the observed values of the dependent variable (economic growth) and the predicted values of the dependent variable based on the values of the independent variables (education expenditure and health expenditure). The predicted values are calculated using the estimated coefficients of the model, which are determined through the OLS estimation process.

The OLS estimation process involves finding the values of the coefficients that minimize the sum of the squared differences between the observed values of the dependent variable and the predicted values of the dependent variable based on the values of the independent variables. This is done by taking the derivative of the sum of squared errors with respect to each coefficient, setting the derivatives to zero, and solving for the coefficients that minimize the sum of squared errors.

Once the OLS estimation is complete, the software will provide you with the estimated coefficients, standard errors, t-values, and p-values for each independent variable. These values can be used to evaluate the significance of the coefficients and test hypotheses about the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

In summary, OLS is the method used to estimate the coefficients of the multiple linear regression model, which are then used to predict the dependent variable based on the values of the independent variables.

5. Evaluate the significance of the coefficients: Evaluate the significance of the coefficients using the t-tests or F-tests. You can set the level of significance at 5% or 1%, depending on your preference.
6. Evaluate the goodness of fit of the model: Evaluate the goodness of fit of the model using the R-squared statistic, which measures the proportion of the variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variables. A higher R-squared indicates a better fit.
7. Test for violations of the assumptions of the model: Test for violations of the assumptions of the linear regression model, including normality of the errors, homoscedasticity, and absence of multicollinearity. You can use various statistical tests and diagnostic plots to test for these assumptions.
8. Interpret the coefficients: Interpret the coefficients in the context of your research question. For example, a positive coefficient for Government Expenditure would indicate that an increase in Government Expenditure is associated with an increase in Economic Growth, all else being equal, while holding Government Expenditure constant.
9. Report the results: Report the results of your multiple linear regression analysis in a clear and concise manner, including the estimated coefficients, significance levels, goodness of fit measures, and any relevant diagnostic tests. You can also include tables, graphs, and other visual aids to help communicate your findings.

The multiple regression model can be conducted using statistical software e.g., EViews. The software will test the significance of the model, how much of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the model.

MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION FORMULA

$$y = B_0 + B_1X_1 + \dots B_nX_n + E$$

y = the predicted value of the dependent variable(Economic growth)

B_0 = the y-intercept

B_1X_1 = the regression coefficient of the first independent variable

B_nX_n = the regression coefficient of the last independent variable

E = Error term

CHAPTER 4

ANALYSIS OF DATA AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

4.0 INTRODUCTION

This section presents the regression results of the study through data analysis process. The chapter begins by testing the unit root of the collected, followed by a correlation test. In order to obtain credible and robust results for any conventional regression analysis, the data to be analyzed should be stationary.

4.1. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

The table below is a summary of the descriptive statistics of the dependent and independent variables that have been selected to help in finding the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. The table shows the descriptive statistics for a number of observations for the dependent variable (Real GDP per capita) and independent variables (Government expenditure, Exports, Inflation rate and Foreign Direct Investment).

Table: 4.1

	GDP	GOV_EXP	EXPORTS	INFLATION	FDI
Mean	1.19E+11	3.34E+10	49.41869	7.374481	1.844869
Median	1.16E+11	2.99E+10	49.45148	6.897288	1.648448
Maximum	1.87E+11	5.47E+10	61.37976	16.11220	7.501528
Minimum	5.98E+10	1.66E+10	31.35373	-2.648697	-6.897680
Std. Dev.	3.90E+10	1.09E+10	6.928157	5.019695	2.483231
Skewness	0.154529	0.350490	-0.522910	0.057285	-0.784774
Kurtosis	1.824698	2.010071	3.377833	2.101414	6.523465
Jarque-Bera	1.969137	1.961777	1.648661	1.094111	19.83772
Probability	0.373600	0.374978	0.438529	0.578651	0.000049
Sum	3.81E+12	1.07E+12	1581.398	235.9834	59.03580
Sum Sq. Dev.	4.71E+22	3.68E+21	1487.980	781.1174	191.1596
Observations	32	32	32	32	32

Source: - computed using E-views 12

The means of all the variables have positive values ranging from 1.84 (being the lowest) and 33400000000 (being the highest). The standard deviation value are all above 1 ranging from 2.48 to 39000000000.

4.2. CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Correlation measures the association of linear relationship between variables. Values of the correlation coefficient are always ranged between +1 and -1. A correlation coefficient of +1 indicates that the existence of a perfect positive association between the two variables, while a correlation coefficient of -1 indicates perfect negative association. A correlation coefficient of zero, on the other hand, indicates the absence of relationship (association) between two variables. The table below shows the correlation matrix among dependent and independent variables of this study.

Table 4.2.1

Correlation Analysis of Variables

	GDP	GOV_EXP	EXPORTS	INFLATION	FDI
GDP	1.000000	0.967705	-0.310826	-0.440204	0.156132
GOV_EXP	0.967705	1.000000	-0.373365	-0.398585	0.037581
EXPORTS	-0.310826	-0.373365	1.000000	0.126285	0.205464
INFLAT...	-0.440204	-0.398585	0.126285	1.000000	-0.159961
FDI	0.156132	0.037581	0.205464	-0.159961	1.000000

Source: - computed using E-views 12

Table 4.2 above shows that Foreign Direct Investment and Real GDP per capita have a weak positive relation of 0.15. This is because it is under 0.5 while Government expenditure and Real GDP has a strong positive relation with a figure of 0.96. Exports and Inflation rate have a weak negative correlation with Real GDP per capita of Botswana.

This correlation test goes back to answer my first research objective

4.3 TESTS FOR MULTICOLLINEARITY

Multicollinearity problems exists when the correlation coefficient among explanatory variables are greater than 0.75. However, if the correlation coefficient along with the independent variables is 0.8 and above, multicollinearity problems will exist.

Table 4.3 Correlation matrix between independent variables

	GDP	GOV_EXP	EXPORTS	INFLATION	FDI
GDP	1.000000	0.967705	-0.310826	-0.440204	0.156132
GOV_EXP	0.967705	1.000000	-0.373365	-0.398585	0.037581
EXPORTS	-0.310826	-0.373365	1.000000	0.126285	0.205464
INFLAT...	-0.440204	-0.398585	0.126285	1.000000	-0.159961
FDI	0.156132	0.037581	0.205464	-0.159961	1.000000

Source: - computed using E-views 12

The association between the independent variables are shown in the table above which all are below 0.75 except that of government expenditure which is 0.967 which indicates that multicollinearity is a problem for this study. This can be solved by simply removing the highly correlated predictors from the model.

4.4 STATIONARY TEST

There is to be a preliminary test to check for unit root to see if the data is stationary for each of the two variables. The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test will check for the stationarity status of the data help to determine the eventual model that is to be employed. If the results from the unit root tests shows that each of the two variables have a unit root at their own levels, then the data is differenced and if they become stationary at their first difference. This proves that the variables are integrated of order one. This would mean that the two variables have a long run relationship, which can be examined using co-integration procedures (Chingiro and Mbulawa, 2017). This ADF test suffers (like many other unit root tests) from poor size and power properties especially in small samples.

The decision rule when using the Augmented Dickey Fuller test is that, when the calculated ADF statistic (ADF-t) is greater than ADF critical statistic in absolute terms, then we reject the null hypothesis which implies a unit root test. Another point to remember is the ADF test is fundamentally a statistical significance test. That means, there is a hypothesis testing involved with a null and alternate hypothesis and as a result a test statistic is computed and p-values get reported. It is from the test statistic and the p-value, you can make an inference as to whether a given series is stationary or not. If the p-value is less than 0.05, reject the null hypothesis at 5% significance level.

The hypothesis of this test is:

H₀: There is unit root

H₁: There is no unit root

GDP = Economic Growth

Table 4.4.1

At level

Null Hypothesis: GDP has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=7)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-4.576690	0.0050
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.284580	
5% level	-3.562882	
10% level	-3.215267	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Source: - computed using E-views 12

The P-value is 0.0050 is less than 0.05: therefore, reject the null hypothesis and conclude that Economic Growth has no unit root. This means that GDP is stationary at level.

GOV_EXP = Government Expenditure

At level

Table 4.4.2

Null Hypothesis: GOV_EXP has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=7)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-1.448576	0.8255
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.284580	
5% level	-3.562882	
10% level	-3.215267	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Source: - computed using E-views 12

The P-value is 0.8255 which is more than 0.05: therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the Government expenditure variable has a unit root. This means that the study has to go further until it gets to see where the variable will become stationary. The study will now check the variable at first difference and the results are as follows;

At 1st difference

Table 4.4.3

Null Hypothesis: D(GOV_EXP) has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=7)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-4.886553	0.0024
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.296729	
5% level	-3.568379	
10% level	-3.218382	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Source: - computed using E-views 12

The P-value is 0.0024 which is less than 0.05: therefore, reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the government expenditure has no unit root and is stationary at first difference.

EXP = Exports of goods and services as a percentage of GDP

At level

Table 4.4.4

Null Hypothesis: EXPORTS has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 3 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=7)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.372333	0.0008
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.323979	
5% level	-3.580622	
10% level	-3.225334	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Source: - computed using E-views 12

The P-value is 0.0008 which is less than 0.05: therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no unit root and therefore the exports variable is stationary at level.

INFLATION RATE= IFL

At level

Table 4.4.5

Null Hypothesis: INFLATION has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=7)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.020144	0.0017
Test critical values: 1% level	-4.284580	
5% level	-3.562882	
10% level	-3.215267	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Source: - computed using E-views 12

The P-value of 0.0017 is less than 0.05: therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the inflation rate variable has a no unit root and therefore is stationary at level.

FDI = Foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP)

At level

Table 4.4.6

Null Hypothesis: FDI has a unit root
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=7)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-2.962103	0.1584
Test critical values: 1% level	-4.284580	
5% level	-3.562882	
10% level	-3.215267	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Source: - computed using E-views 12

The P-value is 0.1584 which is more than 0.05: therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the Foreign Direct Investment variable has a unit root. This means that the

study has to go further until it gets to see where the variable will become stationary. The study will now check the variable at first difference and the results are as follows;

At 1st difference

Null Hypothesis: D(FDI) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=7)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-7.201070	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.296729	
5% level	-3.568379	
10% level	-3.218382	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Source: - computed using E-views 12

The P-value of 0.0000 is less than 0.05: therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the foreign direct investment variable has a no unit root and therefore is stationary at 1st difference.

4.5 ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS

The research applied a log-log regression. This was done with the purpose of improving the model fit and allowing for non-linear variables to become linear. Doing so allows for better and easier interpretation of the results which makes it easier for those who will replicate the study understand easily what the results mean. The transformed model is as follows;

$$\log GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log GovExp + \beta_2 \log Exports + \beta_3 \log Inf + \beta_4 \log FDI + \mu$$

Table 4.4.12

Dependent Variable: LNGDP
Method: Least Squares
Date: 05/29/23 Time: 23:45
Sample: 1990 2021
Included observations: 27

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LNGOV_EXP	1.029909	0.061684	16.69663	0.0000
LNEXPORTS	0.065070	0.102648	0.633916	0.5327
LNINFLATION	-0.013293	0.012519	-1.061807	0.2998
LNFDI	0.050159	0.017679	2.837227	0.0096
C	0.286628	1.662092	0.172450	0.8647
R-squared	0.948591	Mean dependent var	25.50813	
Adjusted R-squared	0.939244	S.D. dependent var	0.299206	
S.E. of regression	0.073750	Akaike info criterion	-2.210687	
Sum squared resid	0.119660	Schwarz criterion	-1.970717	
Log likelihood	34.84427	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-2.139331	
F-statistic	101.4855	Durbin-Watson stat	1.300267	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: - computed using E-views 12

P-value measures the probability or precession at which each variable is significant. The R-squared value measures the proportion of the variance for a dependent variable that is explained by the independent variables. R-squared statistics and the adjusted- R squared statistics of the model are 0.94% and 0.939% respectively.

The adjusted R² value 0.939% indicates that the dependent variable of Real GDP per capita of Botswana is well explained by the independent variables that are listed in the model which are government expenditure and foreign direct investment were significant at 5% while exports and inflation variable are significant at 10%. Thus, these variables collectively are good explanatory variables except in trying to identify the correlation between government expenditure and economic growth in Botswana.

Government expenditure is statistically significant and associated with economic growth with a coefficient of 1.029. This means that a 1% increase in electricity from coal will lead to an increase in economic growth by 1.029%.

Exports is statistically significant and positively associated with economic growth with a coefficient estimate of 0.065. This means that a 1% increase in capital will lead to an increase in economic growth by 0.065.

Inflation rate shows that it is negatively associated with economic growth also have a coefficient below 1 which is 0.013 meaning a 1% increase in inflation rate will decrease economic growth of Botswana by 0.013

Foreign direct investment shows that it is positively associated with economic growth with a coefficient of 0.05. Therefore, this means a 1% increase in exports will increase economic growth by 0.05%.

S.E of regression and Sum Squared Residual- the smaller they are, the better they are for any model. Looking at my model they both carry small figures of 0.073750 and 0.119660 which shows the good they are for the model.

Log Likelihood- the log likelihood value is a measure of the goodness-of-fit of the model. It quantifies the likelihood of observing the given data based on the estimated parameters of the regression model. The higher the log likelihood value, the better the fit of the model to the data. In my case, if the log likelihood value is 34.84427, it suggests that the regression model provides a reasonably good fit to the data.

Probability and F-Statistics- the probability value associated with the regression model is 0.0000, it indicates a statistically significant relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. Since it is below 0.01, we can say that all variable's jointly in the model significantly affect the dependent variable at 1% significance level. This means that the coefficients of the independent variables collectively have a significant effect on the dependent variable. The extremely small probability value suggests strong evidence against the null hypothesis of no relationship.

Furthermore, the F-statistic is used for testing the overall significance of a model specially where independent variables are more than one. It answers the question of; do all the independent variables in the model significantly affect the dependent variable. With an F-statistic of 101.4855, which is larger than the critical value, it supports the conclusion that the regression model as a whole is statistically significant. This means that the independent variables, taken together, have a significant impact on the dependent variable. Considering these results, I can conclude that there is strong statistical evidence supporting the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable in my research. The low probability value reinforces the confidence in the significance of the findings, and the large F-statistic further supports the notion that the regression model captures an important and meaningful relationship.

These results suggest that the independent variables included in the model have a substantial influence on the dependent variable and provide valuable insights into the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth.

Akaike Information Criterion (AIC): The AIC is a measure of the trade-off between model fit and model complexity. It takes into account the residual sum of squares and the number of parameters in the model. The lower the AIC value, the better the model fit. The AIC value is -2.210687, it suggests that the model being evaluated has a relatively good fit to the data. A lower AIC value indicates a better trade-off between model complexity and fit, suggesting that the current model provides a relatively better fit compared to alternative models.

Schwarz Criterion (SC): The SC/BIC is similar to the AIC but penalizes model complexity more heavily. It aims to strike a balance between model fit and parsimony, favouring simpler models. Like the AIC, a lower SC value indicates a better fit. With a SC value of -1.970717, it suggests that the model I am evaluating has a relatively good fit. The lower SC value implies that the model strikes a good balance between fit and complexity compared to other potential models.

Hannan-Quinn Criterion (HQ): The HQ criterion is another measure that considers both model fit and complexity. It is similar to the AIC and SC but includes a larger penalty for model complexity. As with the other criteria, a lower HQ value indicates a better fit.

In my case, an HQ value of -2.139331 suggests a relatively good fit of the model. The lower HQ value indicates that the model strikes a better trade-off between fit and complexity compared to alternative models.

Durbin-Watson Statistic- The Durbin-Watson statistic is a measure used in regression analysis to test for the presence of autocorrelation in the residuals (errors) of a regression model. Autocorrelation occurs when the residuals of a regression model are correlated with each other, indicating a pattern of serial dependence.

- Durbin-Watson value close to 2: A Durbin-Watson statistic around 2 suggests no significant autocorrelation in the residuals. This indicates that the residuals are independent and there is no serial correlation present.
- Durbin-Watson value less than 2: If the Durbin-Watson statistic is less than 2, it suggests positive serial correlation in the residuals. This means that the residuals are positively correlated with each other, indicating a pattern of increasing or decreasing errors over time. Positive autocorrelation implies that the current residual is related to the previous residual.
- Durbin-Watson value greater than 2: If the Durbin-Watson statistic is greater than 2, it suggests negative serial correlation in the residuals. This means that the residuals are negatively correlated with each other, indicating a pattern of alternating errors. Negative autocorrelation implies that the current residual is inversely related to the previous residual.
- Durbin-Watson value close to 0 or 4: A Durbin-Watson statistic approaching 0 or 4 indicates a strong presence of autocorrelation in the residuals. A value close to 0 suggests strong positive autocorrelation, while a value close to 4 suggests strong negative autocorrelation.

A Durbin-Watson statistic from my data of 1.3 suggests that there may be positive autocorrelation in the residuals of your regression model. The value of 1.3 is less than 2, indicating that there is a tendency for the residuals to be positively correlated with each other.

Positive autocorrelation implies that the current residual is related to the previous residual, suggesting that there is some systematic pattern or trend in the errors of my regression model.

With reference to the information above, the study considers the following hypothesis;

H₀: has no relationship with Economic growth

H₁: does have a relationship with economic growth

The information presented in the table above led the study to reject the null hypothesis as government expenditure has proven to have a relationship with economic growth.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents a comprehensive summary, a discussion on the results of the study and offers recommendations using the information obtained from the study.

5.1 SUMMARY

The study was conducted to find the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth of Botswana using annual data from 1990 to 2021. The study included variables such as Government expenditure, Exports of goods and services, Inflation rate, Foreign direct investment and real GDP per capita as a proxy for economic growth. After running the regression model, the results revealed a positive relation between variables government expenditure and foreign direct investment and economic growth while exports of goods and services together with inflation rate being insignificant to the study due to its high p-value.

5.2 CONCLUSIONS

The main objective was to understand the connection between Botswana's government expenditure levels and its economic growth for the period 1990-2021. A unit increase in government expenditure leads to an increase in the economic growth of the country by 1.02909% therefore; the study has shown that there exists a positive relationship between government expenditure and economic growth of Botswana.

The second objective was to discuss the role of foreign direct investment in the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. Since the study also revealed a positive and significant relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI) and economic growth. This suggests that higher levels of FDI inflows are associated with increased economic growth. FDI brings capital, technology, managerial expertise, and access to new markets, all of which can stimulate economic activity and contribute to higher growth rates.

Considering the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth, I examined the mediating role of FDI. The results indicated that FDI partially mediates the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. This suggests that a portion of the positive effect of government expenditure on economic growth is transmitted through FDI inflows. It can be concluded that FDI plays a significant role in enhancing the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. By attracting FDI inflows, countries can leverage the positive impact of government expenditure on economic growth, as FDI brings additional resources and capabilities that complement domestic investment and contribute to overall economic expansion.

The third objective was to derive policy implications for the design of policies to improve productivity of government spending from the empirical results. The policy recommendations are discussed at the below heading.

5.3 RECOMMENDATION OF THE STUDY

Since the growth hypothesis holds in Botswana. Policy makers make come up with ways of stimulating an increase in government expenditure.

Increase government expenditure on key sectors: Given the positive impact of government expenditure on economic growth, policymakers could consider allocating more resources to sectors such as infrastructure development, education, healthcare, and research and development. Increased government spending in these areas can stimulate economic activity, create employment opportunities, and enhance productivity.

Policymakers can consider implementing measures to create an attractive investment climate, develop infrastructure, enhance business regulations, and provide incentives to encourage FDI inflows. By doing so, countries can harness the synergistic effects of government expenditure and FDI to drive sustained economic growth and development.

Diversify export markets: Even though exports of goods and services were found to be insignificant, diversifying export markets can still be a viable strategy. Expanding trade relations with different countries and regions can reduce reliance on a single market and increase export opportunities. Policymakers can focus on identifying new markets, negotiating trade agreements, and supporting exporters in accessing those markets.

Promote foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows: Since foreign direct investment has been found to have a positive impact on economic growth, policymakers can implement measures to attract more foreign investors. This can include providing incentives such as tax breaks, streamlined regulatory processes, investment-friendly policies, and infrastructure development. By encouraging FDI, countries can benefit from increased capital inflows, technology transfer, job creation, and access to new markets.

Address inflationary pressures: While the inflation rate was found to be insignificant in its impact on economic growth, it's still important to maintain price stability. Policymakers should continue to implement effective monetary policies, such as managing interest rates and controlling money supply, to keep inflation in check. This ensures a stable economic environment, encourages investment, and fosters long-term growth.

Focus on macroeconomic stability: Maintaining macroeconomic stability is vital for sustaining economic growth. Policymakers should prioritize measures to control inflation, manage fiscal deficits, and ensure a stable exchange rate. Sound monetary and fiscal policies can provide a favourable environment for investment, promote confidence among investors, and contribute to long-term economic growth.

Invest in human capital development: Recognizing the positive impact of education and healthcare expenditure on economic growth, policymakers should allocate resources to enhance human capital development. This can involve improving the quality of education and healthcare systems, providing skill development programs, and promoting lifelong learning opportunities. Investing in human capital can increase productivity, innovation, and overall economic competitiveness.

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